

MODERN CIVILIZATION: CHARACTERISTICS AND CHARACTER

Bobir Gulboyev

Researcher of Karshi State University

Bobirgulboyev77@gmail.com.

Tel: (91) 257-90-57

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Abstract: The article explores the concept of civilization, its essence, historical forms and types, and theoretical opinions and considerations. Various approaches and views to the concept of civilization are analyzed, the characteristic features of modern society are revealed.

Key words: Globalization, modern trends, civilization, integration, information society, man-made civilization, religion, culture.

The word "civilization" is related to defining the quality limit in human history. The emergence of this concept is the achievement of European science and literature during the Enlightenment period. But the first concepts of civilization arose much earlier. In ancient times, people began to compare their world with the world of others. Although the ancient period is not defined by the word civilization, they contrasted their level of development with barbarism. Initially, the concepts of culture and civilization were used as synonyms, but gradually a difference between these two terms appeared. For example, the German philosopher I. Kant showed the existence of proximity and difference between these concepts. Many philosophers understood the material and technical achievements of society by the term "civilization", and by the term "culture" only its spiritual values. At the beginning of the 20th century, the German philosopher O. Spengler contrasted the concepts of culture and civilization in his work "The Fading of the European Sun". In his opinion, civilization is the highest stage of culture, after which culture gradually turns into a crisis. The emergence of culture is related to the post-savage era of humanity, while civilization is a historical process, a social phenomenon. The development of civilization leads to the improvement of society, as a result of which this society creates an opportunity to ensure the freedom of citizens. Civilized life civilizes a person and creates conditions for his all-round development. It is difficult to give a precise definition to the category of civilization due to its diversity and many meanings. There are more than a hundred definitions of "civilization", and in each unique definition certain aspects and aspects of social life are emphasized, which serves to fully understand the essence of civilization as a social phenomenon. The historical philosophical essence of the concept of civilization is the unity of the

historical process and the set of material, technical and spiritual achievements of mankind during this process. Civilization also means the stage of the global historical process related to reaching a certain level of sociality.

Today, the concept of civilization is analyzed in different contexts. This creates different approaches and views. The concept of civilization, like the concept of culture, is a concept widely used by the scientific community. The concept of civilization lexically refers to the Latin citizenship, represents a specific stage of social development of civil society, material and spiritual culture, the level of cultural development [1; 441]. It was introduced as a scientific concept during the Enlightenment (XVIII) period. According to J. Starobinsky, the concept of civilization was first used by the French economist Victor Rickety Mirabeau (1715-1789) in his work "Friend of Laws". In 1767, it appeared in the work of the Scottish enlightener Adam Ferguson (1723-1816). A. Fergusson put forward the "level of culture mastery" as a criterion for periodization of the history of primitive society: wildness, barbarism, civilization. Humanity remained in the period of wildness until a long historical period, and after passing to a certain stage, the signs of civilization began to appear. Later, the Swedish scientist S. Nilson slightly corrected and supplemented this periodization: wildness, nomadism (Greek nomads - nomadic, nomadic), farming and civilization. In the encyclopedias of the Enlightenment era, the concept of civilization was combined with the concept of development. French philosophers and enlighteners considered a society based on reason and justice to be a civilized society. Different interpretations of the concept of civilization continued, and from the 18th century the concept of "civilization" took a firm place in the vocabulary of historians. From this period, various theories of civilization began to form. At the beginning of the 19th century, civilizations began to be thought of in plural, which meant recognizing the diversity of the civilizational development of nations. The Scottish historian and philosopher A. Ferguson used the concept of civilization to express a certain stage of world historical development, and the French enlighteners used it in the sense of a society based on reason and justice [3; 298]. In general, civilization refers to the state of man and society in relation to wildness. So what is a civilized society? This is a society based on freedom, justice, reason and law. The development of material culture also plays an important role here. The emergence of the division of labor, the formation of classes and castes, the emergence of commodity-money relations, the emergence of writing, the emergence of states, as well as the processes of the

establishment of new types of family relations in primitive society created a civilized society.

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